

IMPORTANCE OF KASHKADARYA REGION IN UZBEKISTAN'S FOREIGN RELATIONS

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***Annotation:** This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the role of the Kashkadarya region in the system of foreign economic and international relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 1991-2024. It is scientifically substantiated that the development model of the regional economy, which in the early years of independence relied mainly on agriculture and fuel and energy resources, rose to a new level in the subsequent stages through the expansion of international investments, foreign trade, export potential and the activities of enterprises with foreign capital. The research used historical-comparative, statistical, systematic, institutional and economic analysis methods. The results obtained indicate the strategic importance of the region in Uzbekistan's foreign economic policy, its leading position in the export of natural gas, oil, chemical industry, agricultural products and attracting international investments. It was also found that in the context of economic reforms after 2017, the geography of international cooperation of the region has significantly expanded, the export structure has diversified, and the volume of foreign investments has steadily grown. As a result of the research, scientific and practical recommendations were developed aimed at further developing the external relations of the Kashkadarya region.*

***Keywords:** Kashkadarya region, external relations, foreign trade, export, import, investment, international cooperation, economic integration, gas industry, Uzbekistan.*

INTRODUCTION

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, a radical restructuring of the country's foreign policy and foreign economic relations became one of the priority areas of state development. During the former Soviet Union, the centralized economic management system practically limited the ability of regions to independently carry out foreign economic activities. During the years of independence, the gradual transition to a market economy, expanding international cooperation, attracting foreign investment and increasing export potential became important directions of state policy. In these processes, the Kashkadarya region, which is distinguished by its natural resources, industrial potential and geostrategic location, occupies a special place among the regions of the country. Kashkadarya region is located in the south of Uzbekistan and is a region rich in natural gas, oil, sulfur, building materials and agricultural resources. The region is the main producer of the country's natural gas reserves, and through such large industrial enterprises as the Mubarak Gas Processing Complex, the Shurtan Gas-Chemical Complex, and the Dehqanabad Potash Fertilizer Plant, it forms a significant part of the republic's export potential. The activities of these enterprises have a significant impact not only on the development of the domestic economy, but also on the expansion of Uzbekistan's international economic relations, export geography, and foreign investment flows.

As a result of the economic reforms implemented in 1991-2024, the number of enterprises with foreign investment in the region has increased several times. Investment cooperation with China, Russia, Turkey, South Korea, Japan, the United Arab Emirates, Germany, and other countries has expanded. In particular, international projects have been implemented in the energy, gas-chemical, textile, construction materials, and food industries. This has contributed to a significant increase in the region's foreign trade indicators, export volumes, and production potential.

The open economic policy, currency liberalization, improvement of the investment climate, and granting of broad economic powers to the regions implemented in Uzbekistan after 2017 have brought the international economic integration of the Kashkadarya region to a new level. Diversification of the export structure, development of new foreign markets, and development of logistics infrastructure have created qualitatively new trends in the region's foreign economic relations.

Nevertheless, there is a lack of comprehensive studies in the scientific literature on the foreign relations of the Kashkadarya region in 1991-2024 from the perspective of historical evolution. Most of the existing works are aimed at highlighting general economic indicators at the republican level, and the dynamics of foreign economic processes at the regional level, investment development factors, and mechanisms of international cooperation have not been deeply analyzed. This study aims to fill this scientific gap.

The main goal of the study is to scientifically assess the role of the Kashkadarya region in Uzbekistan's foreign relations, foreign trade indicators, export-import structure, foreign investment flows, areas of international cooperation, and their impact on the economic development of the region for the period 1991–2024. To achieve this goal, historical development stages are analyzed, trends in external economic indicators are identified, the main areas of international cooperation are assessed, and scientific conclusions are drawn on future development factors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study used historical, statistical, economic-geographical and institutional approaches to comprehensively assess the place of the Kashkadarya region in the system of foreign relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1991-2024. The methodological basis of the study is regional economics, international economic relations, foreign trade theories and regional development concepts. In particular, the theory of comparative advantage, the concept of economic integration and the

export-oriented development model were used as a scientific basis to assess the foreign economic development of regions. These theoretical approaches made it possible to determine the impact of the natural resource wealth, industrial potential and geographical location of the Kashkadarya region on foreign economic relations.

The empirical basis of the study was formed by the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Kashkadarya Regional Statistics Department, the Ministry of Investments, Industry and Trade, the State Customs Committee, the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and open statistical data from international organizations. Analytical reports of the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund, the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), the Asian Development Bank and other international institutions were also used as scientific sources.

During the study, data on foreign trade turnover, export and import volumes, foreign investments, the number of joint ventures, export composition and main trading partners for the period 1991-2024 were systematically summarized. Statistical data were analyzed using the dynamic series method and their change trends were identified. Comparative analysis assessed the share of the Kashkadarya region in the republic's foreign trade and its place in relation to other regions.

Using the historical analysis method, the development of the region's external relations was divided into three stages. The first stage covered 1991-2000 and was considered the period of transition to a market economy and the formation of foreign economic relations. The second stage, covering 2001-2016, was characterized as a period of industrial modernization and increasing export potential. The third stage, covering 2017-2024, was analyzed as a period of economic liberalization, improvement of the investment climate, and acceleration of international economic integration.

The study examined government decisions, investment programs, and regional development strategies using the content analysis method. Statistical data were also

processed using economic analysis methods to assess structural changes in the structure of exports and imports, the geography of foreign trade, and the dynamics of foreign investment flows.

In order to ensure the reliability of the results obtained, the data were compared with several independent sources. In particular, according to the Kashkadarya Regional Statistics Department, in 2024, China, Turkey, and Russia remained the main partners in the region's foreign trade. Trade turnover with China increased sharply, while export dominance with Russia remained.

The advantage of the methodological approach is that it allows not only to describe statistical indicators, but also to explain the economic, political and institutional factors that influence their formation. Therefore, the results of the study can serve as a methodological basis for developing scientific and practical recommendations for improving regional foreign economic policy and increasing export potential.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The foreign economic relations of the Kashkadarya region were formed and developed during the years of independence, inextricably linked with the priority areas of the country's economic policy. The analysis shows that the development of the region's foreign relations can be divided into three main stages. The first stage covers 1991-2000 and is described as the period of formation of foreign economic relations. The second stage covers 2001-2016 and is characterized by industrial modernization and an increase in export potential. The third stage represents a new stage of international integration as a result of economic reforms implemented in 2017-2024.

In the early years of independence, certain difficulties were observed in the regional industry as a result of the disruption of production ties formed during the former Soviet era. However, it was during this period that a national legal framework regulating foreign economic activity was created, new mechanisms for carrying out

export-import operations were formed, and initial economic guarantees for foreign investors were introduced. As a region rich in natural gas and oil reserves, Kashkadarya region played an important role in ensuring the country's energy security, as well as in the formation of export potential.

During 2001-2016, the regional economy experienced steady growth in industrial production. In particular, modernization work carried out in the deep processing of gas, the chemical industry, the production of building materials, and the textile industry contributed to an increase in export volumes. During this period, the number of enterprises with foreign investment increased significantly. Large investment projects were implemented in the energy and gas and chemical sectors with the participation of companies from South Korea, China, Russia, and Japan. As a result, the geography of the region's foreign trade expanded, and the nomenclature of exported products also diversified.

The economic liberalization policy implemented in Uzbekistan since 2017 has given a new impetus to the international economic relations of the Kashkadarya region. As a result of the liberalization of the foreign exchange market, the improvement of the investment climate, the simplification of customs procedures, and the expansion of state support mechanisms for exporting enterprises, the volume of foreign trade has increased significantly. The region's main export products include natural gas, gas-chemical products, mineral fertilizers, cotton tow, yarn, finished textile products, fruit and vegetable products, and construction materials. An analysis of the export structure shows that in the early years, the main part of exports was raw materials, while in subsequent periods the share of processed industrial products increased. This contributed to an increase in added value and increased the competitiveness of the regional economy in the international market. In particular, polyethylene and other polymer products produced at the Shurtan gas-chemical complex were in high demand in international markets. Mineral fertilizers

produced at the Dekhkanabad Potash Plant began to be exported to Asian and European markets, as well as to Central Asian countries.

The import composition mainly consisted of high-tech equipment, industrial equipment, spare parts, chemical reagents and modern production technologies. This indicates that the regional economy is based on an investment development model. Imported equipment made it possible to modernize industrial enterprises, increase energy efficiency and bring product quality into line with international standards.

An analysis of the geography of foreign trade shows that China, Russia, Turkey, Kazakhstan, South Korea, India and the United Arab Emirates are the main economic partners of the region. In particular, there is a development of industrial investments and technological cooperation with China, an expansion of trade in the textile industry with Turkey, the energy and chemical industry with Russia, and food and building materials with Kazakhstan.

In the structure of foreign investments attracted to the region, the energy, gas and chemical, textile, food industry, construction materials production and logistics sectors have formed as priority areas. These investments have expanded the opportunities for creating new jobs, increasing exports, introducing modern technologies, and deep processing of local raw materials. At the same time, the increase in the number of enterprises with foreign capital established in the region has increased the competitiveness of the region in the international economic arena.

Analysis shows that the foreign economic relations of the Kashkadarya region serve not only as an important factor in accelerating economic growth, but also in strengthening the country's export potential, increasing foreign exchange earnings, and attracting international investments. In particular, the development of the energy and gas-chemical sectors has made the region one of the key regions of Uzbekistan's foreign economic strategy.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study confirm that the Kashkadarya region is one of the strategic regions in the system of foreign economic relations of Uzbekistan. The region's wealth in natural resources, in particular, reserves of natural gas, oil and potassium salts, is one of the main factors shaping its foreign trade potential. While in the early years of independence, foreign economic relations were mainly focused on the export of raw materials, in subsequent periods, the share of products with high added value in the export structure increased due to the modernization of industry and the development of processing industries. This indicates that the regional economy is gradually transitioning to an export-oriented development model.

The analysis shows that the economic reforms implemented since 2017 have had a significant impact on the foreign economic activity of the region. As a result of the liberalization of currency policy, simplification of customs procedures, the introduction of mechanisms to support exporting enterprises, and the creation of favorable conditions for foreign investors, the volume of foreign trade has consistently increased. At the end of 2024, the foreign trade turnover of the Kashkadarya region amounted to 1,146.9 million US dollars. Of this, 514.1 million dollars were exported and 632.8 million dollars were imported, which is an increase of 55.5% compared to 2023.

The geography of foreign trade of the region has also expanded significantly. If in the 1990s trade relations were mainly limited to the CIS countries, today China, Turkey, Russia, Germany, South Korea, India, the United Arab Emirates and other countries have become the main economic partners. As of January-November 2024, foreign trade turnover with China amounted to 285.7 million US dollars, with Turkey - 229.8 million US dollars, and with Russia - 102.1 million US dollars.

At the same time, some systemic problems were also identified during the study. First, the high share of gas and gas-chemical products in the export structure remains dependent on changes in world raw material prices. Second, the share of high-tech products in exports is still low. Third, it is necessary to further develop

logistics infrastructure, effectively use multimodal transport corridors, and implement additional measures to digitize exports.

The investment attractiveness of the region has also increased significantly. Foreign investments attracted to the energy, gas-chemical, textile, food industry, and construction materials industries not only serve to increase production volumes, but also to create new jobs, introduce innovative technologies, and expand the nomenclature of export-oriented products. According to modern economic theories, it is precisely export diversification and technological modernization that are the main factors increasing the international competitiveness of regions.

The future foreign economic development of the Kashkadarya region is closely related, first of all, to increasing the level of deep processing of industrial products, introducing the principles of "green economy", expanding the use of renewable energy sources, and developing digital logistics systems. In addition, active participation in international transport corridors, including the Trans-Afghan Transport Corridor and logistics projects connecting Central Asia with South Asia, will further increase the foreign economic potential of the region. The results show that the Kashkadarya region, as one of the key regions of Uzbekistan's foreign economic policy, is making a significant contribution not only to increasing the volume of national exports, but also to increasing the flow of international investments, the formation of modern industrial sectors, and accelerating the country's global economic integration.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study show that during 1991-2024, Kashkadarya region became one of the regions of strategic importance in the system of foreign economic relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the early years of independence, the region's foreign economic activity was mainly focused on the export of natural resources, but as a result of structural reforms implemented in the subsequent stages,

modernization of production and attraction of international investments, the quality and scope of foreign economic relations significantly expanded.

The analysis shows that the export potential of the region was formed due to the energy, gas and chemical, chemical industry, agriculture and textile sectors. In particular, the activities of such large industrial enterprises as the Shurtan gas and chemical complex, the Mubarak gas processing plant and the Dehqanabad potash plant became an important factor in increasing the competitiveness of the region in international markets. At the same time, the increase in the share of processed products in the export structure indicates that the economy is gradually transitioning from raw material exports to the production of high value-added products.

The economic liberalization policy implemented since 2017, the improvement of the investment climate, the liberalization of the foreign exchange market, and the introduction of export support mechanisms have ensured a stable growth in the region's foreign trade indicators. According to the results of 2024, the foreign trade turnover of the Kashkadarya region reached 1,146.9 million US dollars, with exports amounting to 514.1 million US dollars, and imports amounting to 632.8 million US dollars, which indicates the consistent development of the region's international economic integration.

At the same time, some problems were also identified during the study. The high share of fuel and energy products in the export structure remains dependent on price changes on the world market. In addition, there is a relatively low share of high-tech exports and a need to further improve the logistics infrastructure. In the future, to increase the foreign economic potential of the Kashkadarya region, it is advisable to diversify exports, expand the production of innovative and high-tech products, develop logistics centers, effectively use transport corridors, and direct foreign investments to knowledge-intensive industries. The implementation of these areas will not only strengthen the region's position in Uzbekistan's foreign relations, but also significantly increase its economic competitiveness in Central Asia.

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